

The Influence of Job Satisfaction on the Performance Level of Business Process Outsourcing Work-from-Home Employees

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Abstract

This study investigated the knowledge and This study examined the relationship between job satisfaction and sustainable performance among Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) employees working under full-time work-from-home and hybrid arrangements in Naga City. It assessed job satisfaction through intrinsic and extrinsic motivators based on Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory and Self-Determination Theory, focusing on factors such as achievement, recognition, salary structure, and peer relationships. Employee performance was measured using indicators of autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Using a quantitative research design, data were gathered from 70 respondents, and findings revealed that both hygiene and motivational factors significantly influenced job satisfaction, which strongly correlated with sustainable employee performance. Hybrid

workers reported slightly higher job satisfaction due to increased flexibility and better work-life balance, while some in-office engagement continued to drive motivation.

The study also identified communication barriers, social isolation, and inconsistent policy implementation as key challenges. These results suggest that well-structured motivational strategies and supportive workplace environments can enhance job satisfaction and sustain high performance. In response, the study proposed the H.O.M.E. Project, which stands for Harnessing Opportunities, Motivation, and Engagement for Sustainable Remote Work Excellence, to strengthen leadership, recognition, and infrastructure supporting remote and hybrid work setups.

Keywords: *job satisfaction, work-from-home, hybrid work, BPO industry, performance sustainability, Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, Self-Determination Theory*

INTRODUCTION

Achieving high levels of job satisfaction and work performance is critical for the success of any organization. Across various industries, organizations have recognized that fostering employee motivation

and satisfaction is essential to maintaining productivity and growth, yet challenges remain in understanding the factors that influence these outcomes (Mubarok, 2019). It must be noted that employees today seek more than traditional incentives such as job security and financial compensation; personal fulfilment, career advancement, and meaningful work are increasingly important drivers of motivation and performance (Danendra & Rahyuda, 2019). With all that considered, organizations must prioritize creating work environments that balance intrinsic and extrinsic motivators to support both employee satisfaction and sustained performance.

The Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) sector is one of the largest employers in the Philippines and continues to evolve rapidly, especially with the adoption of remote and hybrid work arrangements. These changes have significant implications for how job satisfaction and performance are understood and managed in this sector. As companies adapt to new work modalities, understanding the complex relationship between motivation, satisfaction, and productivity is vital for maintaining service quality and operational efficiency.

A study examining job satisfaction and work performance in the context of evolving BPO work arrangements is timely and relevant. However, during the research discovery phase, a lack of comprehensive studies focusing on intrinsic and extrinsic motivators within hybrid and remote BPO settings was observed. This gap makes it necessary to pursue further investigation. It is hoped that this study will contribute valuable insights into employee motivation and performance, thereby supporting the development of effective management practices in the BPO industry.

Research Questions

The study determined the influence of job satisfaction on the performance level of employees of the work-from-home (WFH) modality of business process outsourcing (BPOs).

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of job satisfaction of work-from-home employees along the following factors:
 - a. Hygiene factor (Job Dissatisfiers)
 - i. Salary Structure
 - ii. Company Policies
 - iii. Employee benefits
 - iv. Working conditions
 - v. Employment Status
 - vi. Peers Relationship
 - vii. Job Security
 - b. Motivation factor (Job Satisfiers)
 - i. Work Recognition
 - ii. Achievement
 - iii. Growth and Development
 - iv. Duties and Responsibility
 - v. Work Contribution
2. What is the performance level of work-from-home employees along the following:
 - a. Autonomy
 - b. Competence
 - c. Relatedness
3. Does job satisfaction significantly influence the performance level of work-from-home employees?
4. Are there significant differences among the aspects of hygiene and motivation factors and between groups of respondents?
5. What development program/plan may be proposed based from the results of the study?

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study focused exclusively on 70 employees within the Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) industry located in Naga City, specifically 35 employees working in hybrid and 35 working in full-time work-from-home setups. Future research is recommended to extend beyond these boundaries by including other industries and regions to improve the applicability and generalizability of the findings. Additionally, incorporating employees who work fully onsite or in different remote work models would provide a broader perspective on job satisfaction and performance. Increasing the sample size and diversity of respondents could also enhance the robustness of future studies. By addressing these exclusions, subsequent research can offer more comprehensive insights to support organizations across varied sectors and work arrangements.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework presents the level of job satisfaction of work-from-home employees — operationally defined through hygiene factors (extrinsic elements such as salary structure, company policies, employee benefits, working conditions, employment status, peer relationships, and job security) and motivation factors (intrinsic elements including work recognition, achievement, growth and development, duties and responsibility, and work contribution) — as the independent variable. The performance level of work-from-home employees — measured by autonomy (self-direction and choice), competence (tasks and roles that make employees feel capable and effective), and relatedness (sense of connection and belonging with colleagues and the organization) — serves as the dependent variable. Identified relationships between job satisfaction factors and employee performance levels form the basis for the proposed development plan and program, termed the H.O.M.E. Project: Harnessing Opportunities, Motivation, and Engagement for Sustainable Remote Work Excellence, which aims to enhance both job satisfaction and work performance through targeted interventions.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the research method utilized, the study's participants, the research tool, the process, and the statistical analyses performed on the study's data.

Research Design

The study will use standardized and modified questionnaires distributed to three groups: Work-From-Home (Set A), Hybrid employees (Set B), and a third group. The survey consists of two parts: one based on Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory assessing job satisfaction factors, and the other on Self-Determination Theory, examining intrinsic and extrinsic motivators related to autonomy, competence, and relatedness. The descriptive aspect involves detailing participant characteristics and work arrangements. The correlational design explores relationships between job satisfaction and work performance. The evaluative component assesses motivational factors influencing employee satisfaction and productivity through established theoretical frameworks.

Respondents of the Study

The locale of the study includes two sets of participants in this study. They are both located in Naga City, Camarines Sur among identified Business Process Outsourcing companies offering work from home setup. The first set will be composed of 35 regular BPO employees working in a full-time WFH setup. The second will be composed of 35 BPO employees working in a hybrid setup, which is a part-time office and part-time WFH. The third set will include 30 employees in managerial or supervisory positions. The population in this study is composed of 70 regular or probationary employees. The rationale for this decision is based on the fact that Naga City is a metropolitan area where numerous BPO companies have been emerging over time. Hence, there is a possibility of obtaining all the necessary and relevant data from identified companies.

Research Instrument

The research utilized standardized and modified questionnaires were distributed to participant groups: Full Time Work-From-Home and Hybrid employees. The survey consisted of two parts: one based on Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, which assessed job satisfaction factors like working conditions and salary; and the other on Self-Determination Theory, which examined intrinsic and extrinsic motivators related to autonomy, competence, and relatedness.

A pre-survey was conducted to confirm the validity and reliability of the instruments with Cronbach alpha scores shown to be .82.

Data Gathering

The data gathering began when the researcher obtained Graduate School Dean's approval in coordination with the college administrators of the respondent school. Quantitative data were collected via Google Forms, and the data were summarized and computed. Subsequently, the study utilized purely quantitative methodologies for the evaluation of the gathered data. This approach is motivated by the understanding that certain findings will require a subjective assessment of the information acquired, in addition to drawing conclusions through mathematical computations such as percentages, tabulation, and mean.

Statistical Treatment

This research used mean and standard deviation to summarize job satisfaction and work performance among BPO employees under work-from-home and hybrid setups. Regression analysis was applied to determine the predictive relationship between job satisfaction and performance. Lastly, Two-Way ANOVA was used to assess significant differences and interaction effects based on work arrangements and demographic factors.

Research Ethics

Ethical considerations were carefully observed throughout the research. Before data collection began, formal approval was obtained from the graduate school dean and the management of the participating BPO companies to ensure the study was officially authorized and aligned with institutional and organizational standards.

BPO company managers, team leaders, and other survey participants were provided with a consent form at the beginning of the survey. The form outlined the nature and purpose of the study, the data to be collected, and their role as respondents. This process ensured the principle of informed consent was upheld, allowing participants to voluntarily engage with a clear understanding of the study's objectives and procedures.

To protect participant privacy, strict confidentiality measures were enforced. All collected data were securely handled, and personal identifiers were either anonymized or stored with restricted access. These steps ensured that the privacy and trust of all respondents were respected throughout the research.

RESULTS

This part presents the interpretation and analysis of data gathered to discuss the answers to the research problems of the study.

Table 1
Summary on the Level of Job Satisfaction Along Hygiene Factors

Hygiene Factor	Full-time Mean	Hybrid Mean	Full-time and Hybrid Mean	Interpretation
Salary Structure	3.26	2.99	3.13	High
Employee Benefits	3.20	2.96	3.08	High
Company Policy	3.23	3.20	3.22	High
Working Conditions	3.25	3.40	3.33	Very High
Employee Status	3.37	2.97	3.17	High
Peer Relationship	3.27	3.30	3.29	Very High
Job Security	3.30	3.26	3.28	Very High
Mean	3.28	3.13	3.20	High

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 – Very High (VH); 2.51 – 3.25 – High (H); 1.76 – 2.50 – Low (L); 1.00 – 1.75 – Very Low (VL)

Among full-time work-from-home (WFH) employees, the highest-rated hygiene factors were Employee Status (3.37), Job Security (3.30), and Peer Relationship (3.27). These results suggest that WFH employees feel recognized, secure in their roles, and supported by strong peer connections. The high Employee Status score reflects positive perceptions of recognition and promotion, while Job Security and Peer Relationship scores indicate trust in leadership and a strong sense of collaboration.

The lowest-rated factors for WFH employees were Employee Benefits (3.20), Company Policy (3.23), and Salary Structure (3.26). While still relatively high, these scores point to areas needing improvement, particularly in benefit adequacy, policy clarity, and pay fairness.

Hybrid employees rated Working Conditions (3.40), Peer Relationship (3.30), and Job Security (3.26) as their top hygiene factors. These indicate satisfaction with their physical work environment and trust in leadership. However, they gave lower ratings for Employee Status (2.97), Employee Benefits (2.96), and Salary Structure (2.99), which may suggest they feel less recognized and fairly compensated compared to their WFH counterparts.

Both groups value peer relationships and job security, but differ in priorities. Full-time WFH employees place more importance on recognition, while hybrid employees' priorities their work environment. This suggests that recognition strategies should focus on fully remote workers, while improvements to physical setups are essential for hybrid staff.

The lower scores for employee status, benefits, and salary structure among hybrid employees also raise concerns about perceived fairness. These gaps may affect morale and retention if not addressed through clearer communication and more inclusive policies.

Supporting the results, a study by Aboramadan et al. (2020) examined the interplay between organizational culture, innovation, and performance, concluding that a positive cultural environment significantly boosts overall performance by fostering innovation. Their research indicates that when employees work in an environment characterized by mutual respect and cooperative teamwork, the natural by-product is an enhanced capacity for creative problem-solving and strategic thinking.

Van Der Voordt and Jensen (2021) mentioned that workplace comfort, particularly the optimization of environmental conditions like lighting, temperature, and noise control, plays a critical role in preventing employee fatigue and disengagement which supports the current study.

Iragi and Kyongo (2023) supports this by their study as it highlighted the significant role that organizational culture plays in fostering employee innovation and performance. Their research suggests that companies with adaptive cultures that prioritize employee support and flexibility are better positioned to retain talent and sustain competitive advantages. Similarly, Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene Theory reinforces the idea that while workplace conditions, leadership, and organizational policies contribute to job satisfaction, factors such as fair compensation and benefits must not be overlooked.

Also, Tucker (2024) found that while performance rewards lead to immediate boosts in productivity and job satisfaction, loyalty incentives are crucial for fostering long-term commitment and stability within the workforce. Employees who receive regular acknowledgment of their sustained contributions are more likely to feel a deeper sense of belonging and advocacy toward their organization.

As supported by research from Kim and Beehr (2022), transparent and frequent communication, especially in the form of constructive feedback, is key to sustaining motivation, boosting job satisfaction, and reducing turnover. In this regard, the findings of this survey underscore the importance of maintaining regular feedback mechanisms to ensure that employees feel valued and connected to their work and organization, despite the challenges of a remote work environment.

Similarly, a study by Straus et al. (2022) reinforces the notion that access to adequate resources and development opportunities significantly enhances employees' confidence and adaptability in a virtual workspace. These studies collectively underscore that while the organization has succeeded in providing strong growth opportunities, enhancing the consistency and clarity of supervisor feedback could further elevate overall job satisfaction and performance.

Chen et al. (2023) provides strong empirical backing for these findings by demonstrating that higher levels of perceived autonomy are directly linked to increased job satisfaction and work efficiency, particularly in remote work environments. Their research shows that when employees are entrusted with significant decision-making power, they develop a stronger sense of accountability and tend to produce more innovative solutions to workplace challenges. This study underscores the value of autonomy as a key

driver of performance, reinforcing the survey result that indicates a high mean score for freedom and authority.

Bhargavi and Swetha (2024) examined factors affecting employee satisfaction and commitment, highlighting the importance of rewards, stress management, leave policies, benefits, and compensation in enhancing motivation and job satisfaction. This aligns with the survey findings, where employees expressed a strong sense of initiative in improving processes but indicated a slight gap in communicating the importance of their coworkers' contributions.

Kaisara and Bwalya (2020), who emphasized that clear and consistent communication plays a crucial role in enhancing remote employees' performance and job satisfaction. Their study found that when remote employees receive feedback regularly, they feel more connected to their supervisors and the organization, mitigating the sense of isolation that can sometimes come with remote work.

In summary, mean hygiene scores of 3.27 for WFH and 3.20 for hybrid employees reflect generally positive perceptions of the work environment. However, enhancing benefits, compensation, and recognition, especially for hybrid staff, will be important for maintaining satisfaction and long-term engagement.

Table 2
Summary on the Level of Job Satisfaction along Motivation Factors

Motivation Factor	Full-time Mean	Hybrid Mean	Full-time and Hybrid Mean	Interpretation
Work Recognition	3.47	3.47	3.47	VH
Achievement	3.56	3.5	3.53	VH
Growth and Development	3.59	3.47	3.53	VH
Duties and Responsibilities	3.58	3.43	3.51	VH
Work Contribution	3.58	3.49	3.54	VH
Mean	3.56	3.47	3.52	Very High

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 – Very High (VH); 2.51 – 3.25 – High (H); 1.76 – 2.50 – Low (L); 1.00 – 1.75 – Very Low (VL)

Among full-time work-from-home employees, the highest-rated motivation factors reflect a strong emphasis on recognition and personal growth. Support for continuing education and development received an average rating of 3.61, showing that most employees feel encouraged and valued in their learning journey. Feeling adequately challenged in their roles followed closely at 3.57, indicating that the nature of their tasks promotes engagement. Clear and achievable goals scored 3.54, suggesting that expectations are well communicated and contribute to a focused work environment.

In contrast, the lowest-rated factors reveal areas for improvement. The presence of a formal recognition program received a 3.11 rating, suggesting limited effectiveness or visibility. Recognition delivered in a timely and meaningful way scored 3.26, while opportunities for added responsibility were rated 3.31. These lower scores suggest that while employees may feel generally appreciated, structured systems for recognition and advancement may be lacking, potentially affecting long-term motivation.

Hybrid employees demonstrated similar patterns. Support for continuing education and personal growth was rated at 3.56, followed by adequate job challenge at 3.52, and clarity of goals and standards at 3.48.

These results show consistent motivation drivers across different work setups, particularly in areas related to growth, engagement, and role clarity.

However, recognition-based factors remained the lowest for hybrid employees as well. Formal recognition received a score of 3.27, while timely recognition and opportunities for added responsibility were rated 3.33 and 3.29 respectively. These figures indicate that both groups experience similar gaps in formal recognition and career advancement.

Antunes et al. (2023) examined this issue and found that employees who perceive career advancement opportunities as merely additional work without professional growth potential experience decreased motivation and engagement. Their study emphasized that organizations should not only assign additional responsibilities but also ensure that these tasks contribute to an employee's professional trajectory.

Kangas et al. (2023) found that organizations that invest in career development initiatives, such as training programs and structured promotion pathways, experience significantly lower turnover rates among remote employees.

Furthermore, Ferrara et al. (2022) provided additional evidence supporting the significance of autonomy and feedback in remote work environments. Their study examined the psychological well-being of remote employees across various industries, including BPO settings, and found that employees who receive regular, constructive feedback and are granted autonomy in their roles report higher job satisfaction and lower stress levels.

In summary, while both full-time and hybrid employees report strong motivation related to growth, engagement, and clarity, formal recognition systems and advancement opportunities appear underdeveloped. Addressing these areas could further enhance overall motivation, employee satisfaction, and retention across various work arrangements.

Table 3

Summary on the Performance Level of Full Time Work-From-Home and Hybrid Setup Employees along Autonomy, Competence and Relatedness

Performance Level	Full-time Mean	Hybrid Mean	Full-time and Hybrid Mean	Interpretation
Autonomy	3.55	3.61	3.58	VH
Competence	3.58	3.55	3.56	VH
Relatedness	3.58	3.6	3.59	VH
Mean	3.57	3.59	3.58	Very High

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 – Very High (VH); 2.51 – 3.25 – High (H); 1.76 – 2.50 – Low (L); 1.00 – 1.75 – Very Low (VL)

Among full-time work-from-home employees, the highest-rated autonomy statement is “Employees manage to plan their work so they finish it on time,” with a mean score of 3.79. This indicates that most employees feel confident in organizing their workload and meeting deadlines, a key component of productivity in a remote environment. Following closely are “Employees are able to set priorities” and “On their initiative, employees start new tasks when the old tasks are completed,” with scores of 3.67 and 3.62 respectively. These results suggest strong time management, initiative, and a clear sense of responsibility among full-time remote workers.

The lowest-rated autonomy statements for this group include “Employees take on extra responsibilities” at 3.29 and “Employees continuously find new challenges at work” at 3.23. While still moderately positive,

these scores suggest limited opportunities or willingness to expand roles beyond current tasks. The statement “Employees take on challenging tasks when they are available” received a score of 3.38, pointing to potential gaps in either task availability or employee initiative.

For hybrid employees, top autonomy ratings were given to “Employees are able to set priorities” and “Employees take on challenging tasks when they are available,” both at 3.79, followed by “Employees manage to plan their work so they finish it on time” at 3.63. These figures reflect strong prioritization skills and a proactive attitude in managing both remote and in-office tasks.

The lowest scores for hybrid employees were “Employees take on extra responsibilities” at 3.21, “Employees continuously find new challenges at work” at 3.43, and “On their initiative, employees start new tasks when the old tasks are completed” at 3.51. These patterns reveal some similarities with full-time employees in areas related to role expansion and initiative.

Drago and Errichiello (2024) emphasized that when employees are given the flexibility to structure their work schedules, set priorities, and manage their workload independently, they experience higher levels of productivity and job satisfaction. Their study found that employees who have autonomy over their tasks tend to perform better because they can align their work with their personal strengths and working styles.

Silva (2022) explored the impact of competence development among remote BPO employees and found that continuous skill enhancement plays a significant role in boosting employee engagement and performance. Their study emphasized that employees who have access to ongoing training programs, upskilling initiatives, and mentorship opportunities tend to feel more confident in their abilities and are more willing to take on challenging tasks. This aligns with the findings of the present study, where employees strongly agreed with their ability to effectively manage their work responsibilities and embrace challenges.

Mohd Safri et al. (2024) highlights that structured communication, positive interactions, and collaborative team dynamics significantly impact employee motivation and organizational commitment. Their study found that employees who feel connected to their colleagues and managers are more engaged, satisfied, and committed to their roles.

Overall, both groups display high autonomy in planning and prioritizing work, with average scores above 3.60. However, there are shared opportunities to strengthen motivation by encouraging employees to embrace additional responsibilities and seek out new challenges. Supporting this growth may contribute to improved engagement, job satisfaction, and long-term performance across all work arrangements.

Table 4
Influence of Job Satisfaction on the Performance Level of Hybrid Employees

Variables	r	r-square	sig.	Interpretation
Hygiene Factor	0.704	.496	.000	significant predictor
Motivation Factor	0.757	.573	.000	significant predictor

Dependent Variable:
Performance (Hybrid Group)

Job satisfaction significantly influences employee performance, especially in hybrid work settings. This study identifies two key drivers: hygiene factors, which include external conditions such as a supportive work environment, clear communication, and access to resources, and motivation factors, which refer to intrinsic elements like recognition, growth, and achievement.

Regression analysis revealed that hygiene factors have a strong positive correlation with performance ($r = 0.704$), accounting for 49.6 percent of the variation in performance among hybrid employees. This underscores the importance of a well-supported work environment in enabling productivity.

However, motivation factors showed an even stronger relationship with performance. These intrinsic elements had a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.757$, explaining 57.3 percent of performance variation. This suggests that internal drivers such as feeling valued, recognized, and challenged have a greater impact on performance than external support alone.

Both hygiene and motivation factors were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), reinforcing the idea that job satisfaction is shaped by both what the organization provides and how employees experience their roles. While tools and infrastructure are necessary, they are not sufficient to ensure long-term engagement.

For hybrid workers, where direct supervision is limited, intrinsic motivators become even more important. Recognition, growth opportunities, and a sense of purpose help sustain performance and drive commitment. Organizations aiming to maximize productivity should invest not only in resources but also in fostering a culture of appreciation and development.

Table 5
Significant Differences Among the Aspects of Hygiene Factors and Between Groups of Respondents

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Interpretation
aspectshyg	.009	6	.009	.037	.849	No significant difference
groups	.618	1	.618	2.444	.120	No significant difference
aspectshyg* groups	.033	6	.033	.130	.719	No significant difference
Total		13				

This part of the study examined whether performance levels among Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) employees differed based on hygiene factors and work arrangements (hybrid or full-time). Hygiene factors assessed included job security, working conditions, policies, relationships, supervision, structure, and salary, based on Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory.

A Two-Way ANOVA was conducted to analyse the data. Results showed no statistically significant difference among the various hygiene factors, with a p-value of 0.849. This indicates that employees rated their performance consistently, regardless of which hygiene factor was considered.

The comparison between hybrid and full-time employees also showed no significant difference in performance, with a p-value of 0.120 and an F-value of 2.444. While minor variations existed, they were not strong enough to be statistically meaningful.

In addition, the interaction between hygiene factors and work modality yielded a p-value of 0.719. This confirms that the effect of hygiene factors on performance did not depend on whether the employee was working in a hybrid or full-time setup.

In summary, the findings indicate that neither the type of hygiene factor nor the work arrangement had a significant effect on employee performance. The absence of interaction effects further supports this

conclusion. These results suggest that workplace policies, resources, and support were likely applied consistently across both groups, contributing to the uniformity in performance perceptions.

Table 6
 Significant Differences Among the Aspects of Motivation Factors and Between Groups of Respondents

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Interpretation
aspectsmot	.010	4	.003	.038	.895	No significant difference
groups2	.742	1	.688	2.581	.153	No significant difference
aspectsmot*groups	.039	5	.034	.132	.745	No significant difference
Total		10				

This study conducted a Two-Way ANOVA to examine differences among motivation factors achievement, recognition, responsibility, advancement, and the work itself and between respondent groups, as well as their interaction effects.

The ANOVA showed a p-value of 0.895 for motivation factors, indicating no significant differences among them. This suggests respondents value these factors equally, reflecting either a balanced motivational environment or a workforce with similar roles and expectations.

For group differences, the p-value was 0.153, also not significant, despite an F-value of 2.581. This implies group membership does not influence motivational perceptions, supporting the presence of an equitable motivational climate.

The interaction between motivation factors and groups yielded a p-value of 0.745, showing no significant combined effect. Thus, motivation perceptions are consistent across groups.

Overall, the ANOVA results reveal no significant differences among motivation factors, between groups, or their interaction, indicating broadly shared motivational drivers.

These findings support a holistic approach to motivation, where initiatives can be broadly applied without heavy tailoring. However, the absence of significant differences warrants cautious interpretation, as subtle variations may exist undetected due to sample or measurement limits.

Future research using alternative frameworks or mixed methods could uncover deeper insights into motivational dynamics beyond this study's scope.

DISCUSSION

The study found that work-from-home employees report positive satisfaction levels with hygiene factors (mean = 3.42) and motivation factors (mean = 3.47). Highest-rated hygiene was the cleanliness and maintenance of the facility (3.69), while pay fairness scored lowest (2.94). For motivation, employees valued freedom and authority most (3.54), but opportunities for added responsibility were rated lowest (3.29). Performance levels averaged 3.59, with autonomy scoring highest (3.69) and willingness to take on extra tasks lowest (3.43).

These results indicate that employees generally feel supported, empowered, and motivated. However, concerns about compensation fairness and career growth opportunities suggest areas needing improvement. The strong correlations between job satisfaction and performance—especially the notable influence of hygiene factors for full-time remote employees ($r = 0.836$) and motivation factors for hybrid employees ($r = 0.757$) highlight the importance of balancing external support with intrinsic motivators. No significant differences were found between employee groups, suggesting that motivational needs are consistent across work arrangements.

It is recommended that organizations review and improve compensation structures to ensure fairness, develop clear career advancement pathways, and strengthen recognition programs. Enhancing communication, leadership training, and peer collaboration will further support employee motivation. Adopting a holistic approach that addresses both hygiene and motivation factors will foster a more engaged and high-performing remote workforce.

REFERENCES

- Mubarok, E. S. (2019). The Effect of Organizational Culture and Work Motivation on Employee Performance: The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction. *European Journal of Business and Management*; <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/The-Effect-of-Organizational-Culture-and-Work-on-of-Mubarok>
- Danendra, A. & Rahyuda, A. (2019). The Effect of Work Loads on Employee Performance With Job Satisfaction As A Mediation Variable. *Journal of Business Management and Economic Research*; <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/The-Effect-of-Work-Loads-on-Employee-Performance-As-Danendra-Rahyuda>
- Aboramadan et al. (2020). Organizational culture, innovation and performance: a study from a non-western context | Emerald Insight. (2019). *Journal of Management Development*, 39(4), 437–451. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMD>
- Van Der Voordt, T., & Jensen, P. A. (2021). The impact of healthy workplaces on employee satisfaction, productivity and costs. *Journal of Corporate Real Estate*, 25(1), 29–49. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jcre-03-2021-0012>
- Iragi, C., & Kyongo, J. (2023). ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND INNOVATION: AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION. *International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovations*, 11, 214–219. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10439019>
- Tucker, B. (2024). Human Resources Strategies to Promote Employee Retention and Human Resources Strategies to Promote Employee Retention and Reduce Turnover *Reduce Turnover*. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu>
- Kim, M., & Beehr, T. A. (2022). Empowering leadership improves employees' positive psychological states to result in more favorable behaviors. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 34(10), 2002–2038. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2022.2054281>
- Straus, E., Uhlig, L., Kühnel, J., & Korunka, C. (2022). Remote workers' well-being, perceived productivity, and engagement: which resources should HRM improve during COVID-19? A

- longitudinal diary study. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 34(15), 2960–2990. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2022.2075235>
- Chen, X., Mamun, A. A., Hussain, W. M. H. W., Jingzu, G., Yang, Q., & Shami, S. S. a. A. (2023). Envisaging the job satisfaction and turnover intention among the young workforce: Evidence from an emerging economy. *PLoS ONE*, 18(6), e0287284. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0287284>
- Bhargavi, M., & Swetha, G. (2024). A Study On Level Of Job Satisfaction Of Employees Working In Bpo Companies. *International Journal of Progressive Research in Engineering Management and Science*, 04(06). <https://doi.org/10.58257/ijprems>
- Kaisara, G., & Bwalya, K. J. (2020). Investigating the E-Learning Challenges Faced by Students during Covid-19 in Namibia. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 10(1), 308. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe>
- Antunes, E. D., Bridi, L. R. T., Santos, M., & Fischer, F. M. (2023). Part-time or full-time teleworking? A systematic review of the psychosocial risk factors of telework from home. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1065593>
- Kangas, H., Heini Pensar, & Rousi, R. (2023). I wouldn't be working this way if I had a family - Differences in remote workers' needs for supervisor's family-supportiveness depending on the parental status. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 147, 103939–103939. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2023.103939>
- Ferrara, B., Pansini, M., De Vincenzi, C., Buonomo, I., & Benevene, P. (2022). Investigating the Role of Remote Working on Employees' Performance and Well-Being: An Evidence-Based Systematic Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(19), 12373. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph191912373>
- Drago, C., & Errichiello, L. (2024, March 29). Remote Work Admist the Covid-19 outbreak: Insights from an Ensemble Community-Based Keyword Network Analysis. *Social Science Research Network*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4777889>
- Silva, I. (2022). "Remote Working Models and their impact on employee performance levels." <https://norma.ncirl.ie/5916/1/ivansilva>
- Mohd Safri, S., Azizi Salleh, M. A., & Mohd Salleh, M. S. (2024). A Study on Remote Working of Employee Motivation and Productivity. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 14(8). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v14-i8/21645>